

Combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizer on maize (*Zea mays* L.) production and reduce N₂O emission

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ABSTRACT

Maize is a cereal plant, it has economic value as a source of carbohydrates and protein after rice. Application of organic matter is expected to improve yield and reduced N₂O emissions. The objective of this study was to determine the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizer in maize cultivation with high yields and low N₂O emissions. The experiment was conducted at Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute, Pati, Central Java on July 2016 - October 2017. The research used Randomized Block Design (RBD) with DK-77 variety, 6 treatments and 3 replications. Fertilization treatments: 1) farmyard manure + phonska + urea prill, 2) farmyard manure + phonska + urea coated biochar, 3) biocompost + phonska + urea prill, 4) biocompost + phonska + urea coated biochar, 5) sludge + phonska + urea prill, 6) sludge + phonska + urea coated biochar. Organic fertilizer rate: farmyard manure 3 ton/ha, biocompost 3 ton/ha (biochar : compost, 1 : 4) and sludge 3 ton/ha. Inorganic fertilizer rate: phonska 300 kg/ha, urea prill 200 kg/ha and urea coated biochar 200 kg/ha (urea : biochar, 4 : 1). Variables observed were yield components, daily flux N₂O and plant height. Emitted gas was collected at every 2 and 4 days after fertilizing application and every 2 weeks simultaneously with plant height. N₂O gas were analyzed by using gas chromatography equipped with electron capture detector (ECD). Results showed, there were no significant different between the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizer on yield and N₂O emissions from maize cultivation.

Keywords: *Maize crop, N₂O emission, organic and anorganic fertilizer*

INTRODUCTION

Increasing of maize production can be improved by using superior varieties and addition of soil organic matter. Fertilizers are usually applied to soil for increasing crop yields to meet the increasing demand of food. Providing organic fertilizer would increase soil fertility and plant growth. The addition of organic matter would improve soil organic carbon. The application could enrich and nourish the soil with increasing number of positive microbes in the soil and could improve yield. Soil organic carbon content was higher in organic manure

and compost application compared to same inorganic fertilizers rate (Gregorich et al., 2001).

The current existing maize cultivation practices are considered to contribute greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), mainly N₂O. It is expected that application of organic and inorganic fertilizers can affect of N₂O emissions from crop cultivation. Increasing use N from inorganic fertilizer in the soil contribute to increase N₂O emission. N₂O is the third most important greenhouse gases and has 298 times the radiative forcing potential of CO₂ (IPCC, 2013). The objective of inorganic fertilizer as urea increased crop production. But also, could increase N₂O emission from high rate of inorganic fertilizer application in the soil (Tongwane et al., 2016).

Application of organic and inorganic fertilizers can increase the activities of soil micro-organisms and enzymes and soil available nutrient contents in the soil (Saha et al., 2008; He and Li 2004). The objective of this study was to determine the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizer in maize cultivation with high yields and low N₂O emissions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The study was conducted at Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute (IAERI) in Pati, Central Java (6°46'39.7 "S and 111°11'53.0" E) on July to October 2017. The location has a climate characteristic with annual mean rainfall of <1500 mm and soil classification as silt loam, Aeric Endoaquepts.

Experimental Design and Maize Cultivation

The six treatments were arranged in randomized complete block design with three replications. The treatments were 1) farmyard manure + phonska + urea prill, 2) farmyard manure + phonska + urea coated biochar, 3) biocompost + phonska + urea prill, 4) biocompost + phonska + urea coated biochar, 5) sludge + phonska + urea prill, 6) sludge + phonska + urea coated biochar. Organic fertilizer rate were farmyard manure 3 ton ha⁻¹, biocompost 3 ton ha⁻¹ (biochar : compost ratio, 1 : 4) dan sludge 3 ton/ha. Organic fertilizer analysis presented in table 1. Inorganic fertilizer rate were phonska 300 kg/ha, urea prill 200 kg ha⁻¹ and urea coated biochar 200 kg/ha (urea : biochar ratio, 4 : 1). The experimental plot size is 5 m x 6 m, plant spacing 70 cm x 20 cm with 2 seeds DK-77 per hole.

Maize irrigation is carried out periodically with water pumps equipped with pipes in each experimental plot. Application of organic fertilizer such as manure, biocompost and sludge is given at the planting day. Organic fertilizer

analysis is shown at table 1. Phonska, inorganic fertilizer is given 15 days after planting (1st fertilization) and urea prill or urea coated biochar are given 50 days after planting (2nd fertilization).

N₂O Measurements, plant height and yield components

N₂O fluxes were measured by a closed chamber method. The size of chamber made of Plexiglas was 40 cm length × 20 cm width × 30 cm height. Gas samples were collected at 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 min after the chamber deployment between 6:00-8:00 am. The samples taken by a 20-ml syringe were stored in 10 ml evacuated glass vials, and then subjected to the laboratory analysis using gas chromatography (GC). Emitted gas was collected at every 2 and 4 days after fertilizing application and every 2 weeks simultaneously with plant height.

The calculation of flux N₂O emissions used a formula adopted from IAEA (1992):

$$E = \frac{dc}{dt} \times \frac{V_{ch}}{A_{ch}} \times \frac{mW}{mV} \times \frac{273,2}{273,2 + T}$$

Here:

E : N₂O flux (mg m⁻² day⁻¹),

dc/dt : Rate of change of concentration with time (t) in the chamber (ppm/min),

mW : Molecular weight of N₂O (g),

mV : Molecular volume at standard temperature and pressure (22,41 l),

V_{ch} : Volume of chamber (m³),

A_{ch} : Chamber area (m²),

T : Average air temperature inside the chamber during gas sampling (°C),

273.2 : Standard temperature Kelvin.

The calculated of total N₂O emissions used a trapezoidal integration method. This method is a linear interpolation and numerical integration between sampling times (Minamikawa et al., 2015).

The yield of harvested maize was measured from 5.6 m² sampling in each plot. The harvested components were length of cob, yield of maize (cob + seeds) harvest, biomass, weight of shelled maize seeds and dry cob and weight of 100 maize seeds. Supporting data observed were plant height data measured every 2 weeks.

Table 1. Organic fertilizer analysis

Organic Fertilizer	C-	N-Total	P-Total	K-Total	pH
	Organic				
%					
Biochar	19.59	0.04	0.15	0.20	7.22
Farmyard	10.14	0.17	0.21	0.98	6.58
Sludge	12.87	0.22	0.13	1.07	6.41
Biocompost	8.90	0.18	2.41	0.40	6.20

Statistical analysis

We conducted an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a randomized block design. Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was performed with a significance level of 0.05 to test differences. Statistical data analysis used SAS (System Analysis Statistics) software.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Plant Growth

DK 77 variety is hybrid maize which is resistant to downy mildew and has a potential yield of 12.6 ton ha⁻¹. The growth of DK-77 variety with a combination of organic and inorganic fertilizers showed not significant difference in plant height (Table 2).

Table 2. Plant height of DK-77 variety

Treatment	Days After Planting (DAP)					
	17 DAP	24 DAP	38 DAP	52 DAP	66 DAP	81 DAP
1	35.75 a	55.46 a	140.25 a	182.58 a	197.92 a	197.75 a
2	36.79 a	55.92 a	138.29 a	191.75 a	201.00 a	208.67 a
3	37.46 a	59.25 a	143.79 a	192.50 a	206.67 a	207.08 a
4	37.71 a	58.29 a	146.13 a	191.96 a	212.88 a	212.42 a
5	36.88 a	55.83 a	134.42 a	187.13 a	189.25 a	194.63 a
6	41.00 a	57.63 a	138.42 a	183.67 a	202.33 a	202.08 a

Note: 1. farmyard manure + phonska + urea prill, 2. farmyard manure + phonska + urea coated biochar, 3. biocompost + phonska + urea prill, 4. biocompost + phonska + urea coated biochar, 5. sludge + phonska + urea prill and 6. sludge + phonska + urea coated biochar.

Providing organic matter is believed to increase crop yields and improve soil fertility. Application of organic and inorganic fertilizers could reduce

fertilizer application, increase the nutrient use efficiency, reduce leaching of nutrients, provides nutrient availability to crops and soil structure which enhances root growth, exchange of gases, nutrient uptake and water (Usman et al., 2015). The use of organic and inorganic fertilizers in the combination (50:50) would produce higher yields than the sole application of either fertilizer or manure particularly (Nasim et al., 2012).

The yield of the DK-77 variety of maize in the form of ear lengths, biomass and shelled corn seeds is shown in table 3. The results of dry shelled corn ranged from 6.7-7.29 t/ha. The highest dry biomass was found in farmyard manure and urea coated biochar by 3.8 ton ha⁻¹ while the highest dry shelled seed yield in biocompost and urea coated biochar treatment was 7.29 t/ha.

Table 3. Yield components and N₂O emission of DK-77 variety

Treatment	length of maize cobs (cm)	Biomass (ton ha ⁻¹)	Maize Yield (ton ha ⁻¹)	Dry cobs (ton ha ⁻¹)	Dry shelled maize (ton ha ⁻¹)		100 grain maize (g)	N ₂ O emission (kg ha ⁻¹ season ⁻¹)
					MC : 14-15%			
1	18.67	a 10.61	a 12.98	a 1.85	a 7.00	a 26.90	b 1.20	a
2	17.92	a 11.32	a 13.64	a 1.80	a 7.21	a 27.50	ab 1.18	a
3	19.83	a 10.56	a 13.61	a 1.87	a 7.29	a 28.87	a 1.51	a
4	19.08	a 11.06	a 12.83	a 1.65	a 6.70	a 27.20	b 1.39	a
5	18.58	a 9.97	a 13.10	a 1.68	a 6.72	a 26.87	b 1.31	a
6	17.92	a 9.85	a 12.78	a 1.65	a 6.75	a 27.77	ab 1.32	a

Note: 1. farmyard manure + phonska + urea prill, 2. farmyard manure + phonska + urea coated biochar, 3. biocompost + phonska + urea prill, 4. biocompost + phonska + urea coated biochar, 5. sludge + phonska + urea prill and 6. sludge + phonska + urea coated biochar.

The application of 3 different types of organic material (farmyard manure, biocompost and sludge) and the use of inorganic fertilizer (urea coated biochar) produced different N₂O daily flux values. The daily flux of N₂O in the maize crop with various fertilizer treatments can be seen in Figure 1. N₂O flux at the beginning of the vegetative phase is higher than the generatif phase. Fertilizer gives a positive response to the value of the N₂O flux released.

The application of biocompost as organic matter produced the highest average value of N₂O flux. The highest flux value is found in biocompost and urea prill treatment, which is 2.77 mg/m². N₂O emissions of DK-77 variety ranged from 1.02-1.42 kg/ha/ season. The lowest N₂O emissions were found in farmyard manure with urea coated biochar, while the highest was in biocompost with urea prill (Table 3). The use of urea coated biochar could slow the release of nutrients, so that N₂O emissions were 2-4% lower compared to urea prill.

Figure 1. N₂O fluxes from DK-77 variety with organic and inorganic fertilization

Note: 1. farmyard manure + phonska + urea prill, 2. farmyard manure + phonska + urea coated biochar, 3. biocompost + phonska + urea prill, 4. biocompost + phonska + urea coated biochar, 5. sludge + phonska + urea prill and 6. sludge + phonska + urea coated biochar.

CONCLUSION

Combination of organic and inorganic fertilizer were no significant different on plant growth, yield components and N₂O emissions from maize cultivation. Maize production of DK-77 variety ranges 12.78 - 13.64 t/ha with shelled maize seeds 6.72 - 7.29 t/ha. Reduction of N₂O emission from urea coated biochar application was 2 - 4%.

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